

Behaviour of Nitrophenols with *p*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride. Part III.

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In the previous papers on this subject (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2481; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9,55) it was shown that when *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride acts on nitrophenols in presence of diethylaniline, the OH group is replaced by Cl atom provided that nitro groups are present in the *ortho* and *para* positions with respect to OH group. It was also shown that the presence of a CH₃ group in the *meta* position with respect to OH acts unfavourably on the replaceability of the OH group. In the present paper we have examined the behaviour of the following phenol derivatives: 2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol; 2:6-dinitrophenol and its halogen derivatives *viz.*, 4-bromo-2:6-dinitrophenol and 4-iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol; 3-chloro-2-bromo-4:6 dinitrophenol; 3-chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol; 3-chloro-2:4:6-trinitrophenol; 3:6-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol; 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-nitrobenzoic acid; 4-hydroxy-3-nitrobenzoic acid and 4-hydroxy-5-bromo-3-nitrobenzoic acid.

The results obtained are given in Table I. The chloro compounds formed contain an active chlorine atom and are capable of undergoing various reactions. These will be described in a later paper. Some of the *p*-toluenesulphonic acid esters are also more or less reactive, while the others are not.

Acetyl and benzoyl derivatives of some phenols used have been described in the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Iodo-4:6-dinitrophenyl-p-toluenesulphonate.—2-Iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol (3.1 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) were boiled together with water and to the hot mass sodium carbonate (1.2 g.) was added in small quantities and the liquid well shaken. The mixture was then allowed to cool and then filtered. The ester (8 g.) dissolved easily in benzene and with difficulty in alcohol from which it crystallises in colourless crystals, m.p. 140°. (Found: S, 6.71. C₁₃H₉O₇N₂IS requires S, 6.9 per cent.).

1-Chloro-2-iodo-4;6-dinitrobenzene.—A mixture of 2-iodo-4;6-dinitrophenol (6 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.1 g.) and diethylaniline (12 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for four hours. From the dark product the diethylaniline was removed by dilute hydrochloric acid and the unchanged phenol by sodium carbonate solution. The crude product (4.5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and the solution boiled with animal charcoal. From the filtered and concentrated solution, the chloriododinitrobenzene separated out in pale white crystals, m.p. 106°. It dissolves in all the common organic solvents. (Found : N, 8.61. $C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl$ I requires N, 8.53 per cent.).

2:6-Dinitrophenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate.—This ester was obtained from 2:6-dinitrophenol (4.6 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (5.2 g.) and sodium carbonate (3 g.) in the manner already described. It dissolves easily in benzene and acetone and with difficulty in alcohol. Colourless crystals from a mixture of alcohol and acetone, m.p. 135°, yield 6 g. (Found : S, 9.15. $C_{13}H_{10}O_7N_2S$ requires S, 9.47 per cent.).

1-Chloro-2:6-dinitrobenzene.—This is obtained from 2:6-dinitrophenol (4.6 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (5.2 g.) and diethylaniline (9 c.c.) in the manner already described. It forms colourless crystals, m.p. 86°, yield 3 g. It dissolves easily in alcohol, benzene, etc. This is identical with the chlorodinitrobenzene prepared by Ostromisslenski (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1908, ii, 78, 261). (Found : N, 13.56 ; Cl, 17.43. $C_6H_3O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 13.83 ; Cl, 17.53 per cent.).

4-Bromo-2:6-Dinitrophenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate.—This was obtained from *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.2 g.), sodium carbonate (2.5 g.) and 4-bromo-2:6-dinitrophenol (5.3 g.). The last compound was obtained from 2:6-dinitrophenol by adding the required amount of bromine to its solution in alcohol (Fromm and Ebert, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1922, ii, 106, 75). The ester, forms colourless crystals, melts at 136°, yield 6 g. (Found : S, 7.84. $C_{13}H_9O_7N_2BrS$ requires S, 7.67 per cent.).

1-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-4-bromobenzene.—This was obtained from 4-bromo-2:6-dinitrophenol (8 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6.4 g.) and diethylaniline (16 c.c.). It is soluble in most of the organic solvents and is obtained as pale white crystals from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 98°, yield 4.8 g. (Found : N, 10.17 ; Cl + Br, 40.74. $C_6H_2O_4N_2Cl$ Br requires N, 9.95 ; Cl + Br, 41.03 per cent.).

4-Iodo-2:6-dinitrophenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate.—This was prepared from 4-iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol (3.1 g.) (Armstrong, *loc. cit.*),

p-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) and sodium carbonate (1.3 g.). Colourless crystals from a mixture of acetone and alcohol, m.p. 138°, yield 4 g. (Found: S, 6.95. $C_{13}H_9O_7N_2IS$ requires S, 6.9 per cent.).

1-Chloro-4-iodo-2:6-dinitrobenzene.—This was obtained from 4-iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol (10.5 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (7 g.) and diethylaniline (22 c.c.). It is soluble in most organic solvents; colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 115°, yield 6 g. (Found: N, 8.86. $C_6H_2O_4N_2ClI$ requires N, 8.53 per cent.).

3-Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol.—To a solution of 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrophenol (6.5 g.) in alcohol, bromine (1.6 c.c.) was added drop by drop. The reaction product was warmed and then poured on ice when chlorobromodinitrophenol (8.3 g.) separated out. It dissolves in most organic solvents and crystallises from methyl alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 9.16. $C_6H_2O_5N_2Cl$ Br requires N, 9.41 per cent.).

3-Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenyl-p-toluenesulphonate, obtained from 3-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol (3 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) and sodium carbonate (1.2 g.), is easily soluble in benzene. Colourless crystals from acetone-alcohol mixture; m.p. 125°, yield 2 g. (Found: S, 7.01. $C_{13}H_8O_7N_2Cl$ BrS requires S, 7.08 per cent.).

1:3-Dichloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene.—This was prepared from 3-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol (6 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.2 g.) and diethylaniline (12 c.c.). Dichlorobromodinitrobenzene dissolves easily in most organic solvents; colourless crystals, m.p. 108°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 9.18. $C_6HO_4N_2Cl_2$ Br requires N, 8.86 per cent.).

3-Chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol.—The compound was prepared by adding iodine (7.6 g.) and mercuric oxide alternately to 3-chloro-4:6-dinitrophenol (6.4 g.) in alcohol. The alcohol was then distilled off and the residue repeatedly extracted with benzene. Chloroiododinitrophenol forms yellow crystals, m.p. 108°, yield 9.5 g. It dissolves in most organic solvents. (Found: N, 7.81. $C_6H_2O_5N_2Cl$ I requires N, 8.13 per cent.).

3-Chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenyltoluenesulphonate.—This was obtained from 3-chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol (3.5 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) and sodium carbonate (1.2 g.). The ester forms colourless crystals, m.p. 150°, yield 3 g. (Found: S, 6.27. $C_{13}H_8O_7N_2Cl$ I S requires S, 6.43 per cent.).

1:3-Dichloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrobenzene.—This was prepared from a mixture of 3-chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol (3.5 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) and diethylaniline (7 c.c.). Dichloriododinitrobenzene is soluble in most organic solvents. Pale white crystals, m.p. 108°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 7.99. $C_6HO_4N_2Cl_2I$ requires N, 7.7 per cent.).

1:3-Dichloro-2:4:6-trinitrobenzene.—This was prepared from a mixture of 3-chloro-2:4:6-trinitrophenol (8 g.) (obtained by nitrating *m*-chlorophenol; cf. Tijmstra *Chem. Zentr.*, 1902, II, 519), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6.3) and diethylaniline (15 c.c.). Colourless crystals, m.p. 129°, yield 6 g. (Sudborough and Picton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 591). (Found: N, 14.63. $C_6HO_6N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 14.89 per cent.).

3:6-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate was prepared from 3:6-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol (2.1 g.) (Kostanecki, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 2321), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) and diethylaniline (15 c.c.). The ester crystallises from acetone-alcohol mixture in colourless crystals, m.p. 137°, yield 3.2 g. (Found: S, 8.97. $C_{15}H_{14}O_7N_2S$ requires S, 8.74 per cent.).

2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-nitromethylbenzoate.—2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-nitrobenzoic acid (5 g.), which was prepared by nitrating 2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (Borsche, *Annalen*, 1904 330, 1000) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (20 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) added to the mixture. The mixture was boiled for three hours, the excess of methyl alcohol distilled off and the residue diluted with ice cold water. The ester crystallises from methyl alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 78°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 6.53. $C_9H_9O_5N$ requires N, 6.63 per cent.).

p-Toluenesulphonic ester of 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-nitromethylbenzoate was obtained from the foregoing methylbenzoate (4.2 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.2 g.), and diethylaniline (9 c.c.). The ester forms colourless crystals, m.p. 93°, yield 6 g. (Found: S, 8.91. $C_{16}H_{15}O_7NS$ requires S, 8.77 per cent.).

2-Phenylamine-4-methyl-5-nitromethylbenzoate.—The foregoing ester (2 g.) and aniline (4 c.c.) were boiled together for a few minutes. On dissolving out the excess of aniline by hydrochloric acid, the phenylaminomethylnitromethylbenzoate separated out. This compound dissolves easily in the common organic solvents and crystallises from alcohol in yellow crystals, m.p. 84°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 9.45. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.79 per cent.).

p-Toluenesulphonic ester of 4-hydroxy-3-nitromethylbenzoate — 4-Hydroxy-3-nitromethylbenzoate (4 g.) (Auwers and Rohrig, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 991; D.R.P. 97334), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (4.2 g.) and diethylaniline (8 c.c.) were heated together on the water-bath. The ester is obtained in colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 86°, yield 6 g. (Found: S, 9.17. $C_{15}H_{13}O_7NS$ requires S, 9.12 per cent.).

4-Phenylamino-3-nitromethylbenzoate.—*p*-Toluenesulphonic ester of 4-hydroxy-3-nitromethylbenzoate (3.5 g.) and aniline (5 c.c.) were heated together for some time. On removing the excess of aniline by hydrochloric acid, the reaction product separated out. Shining yellow crystals from alcohol, m.p. 127°, yield 2.3 g. (Found: N, 10.46. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.30 per cent.).

4-Hydroxy-5-bromo-3-nitrobenzoic acid.—This was prepared by adding bromine (2.7 c.c.) to a solution of 4-hydroxy-3-nitrobenzoic acid (9 g.) (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 408; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1890, ii, 42, 552), in acetic acid (20 c.c.). On adding water to the product of reaction the hydroxybromonitrobenzoic acid separated out (11 g.). It dissolves easily in the common organic solvents; colourless crystals from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 229°. (Found: N, 5.28. $C_7H_4O_5NBr$ requires N, 5.34 per cent.). The methyl ester of the foregoing compound melts at 130°. (Found: N, 5.09. $C_8H_6O_5NBr$ requires N, 5.07 per cent.).

p-Toluenesulphonic ester of 4-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-bromomethylbenzoate.—This was obtained from 4-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-bromomethylbenzoate (2.8 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.1 g.) and diethylaniline (5 c.c.). The ester dissolves easily in most organic solvents; colourless crystals, m.p. 127°, yield 3.6 g. (Found: S, 7.41. $C_{15}H_{12}O_7NBrS$ requires S, 7.44 per cent.).

4-Phenylamino-3-nitro-5-bromomethylbenzoate.—The foregoing ester (2.2 g.) and aniline (5 c.c.) were heated together for sometime. On removing the excess of aniline, the phenylamine derivative separates out (1.5 g.). Deep yellow shining crystals from alcohol, m.p. 128°. (Found: N, 8.06. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N_2Br$ requires N, 7.98 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative of 2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol was obtained in shining colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 113°. (Found: N, 7.68. $C_8H_5O_6N_2I$ requires N, 7.96 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative of 2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol formed colourless crystals from dilute alcohol, m.p. 94°. (Found: N, 7.39. $C_{13}H_7O_6N_2Br$ requires N, 7.63 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative of 4-iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol was obtained in colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 6.98. $C_{13}H_7O_6N_2I$ requires N, 6.76 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative of 3:6-dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol formed colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 102°. (Found: N, 10.89. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6N_2$ requires N, 11.02 per per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative gave colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 124°. (Found: N, 8.63. $C_{15}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires N, 8.86 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative of 4:6-dinitro-m-cresol (OH=1, CH₃=3): gave colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 95°. (Found: N, 9.19. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6N_2$ requires N, 9.27 per cent.).

Acetyl derivative of 2-chloro-4:6-dinitro-m-cresol (OH=1, CH₃=3) gave colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 10.46. $C_9H_7O_6N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.2 per cent.).

Benzoyl derivative of 2-chloro-4:6-dinitro-m-cresol (OH=1, CH₃=3) gave colourless crystal from alcohol, m.p. 117°. (Found: N, 8.13. $C_{14}H_9O_6N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.32 per cent.).

TABLE I.

Phenols.	Product of reaction with <i>p</i> -toluenesulphonyl chloride.		Ester-reactive or not.
	Ester.	Chloro-compound.	
*1. 2:4:6-Tribromophenol	Formed.	...	Not reactive.
*2. 2:4-Dibromo-6-nitrophenol	"	...	"
*3. 2:6-Dibromo-4-nitrophenol	"	...	"
†4. 2:6-Dinitro- <i>m</i> -cresol (OH=1)	"	...	Reactive
†5. 2-Bromo-4:6-dinitro- <i>m</i> -cresol (OH=1)	"	Formed	"
*6. 4-Chloro-2:6-dinitro- <i>m</i> -cresol (OH=1)	"	...	Not reactive
7. 3:6-Dimethyl-2:4-dinitrophenol	"	...	"
*8. 2-Bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol	"	Formed	Reactive
9. 2-Iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol	"	"	"

* *cf. J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2482.† *cf. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 300.

TABLE I—*contd.*

Phenols.	Product of reaction with p-toluenesulphonyl chloride.		Ester-reactive or not.
	Ester.	Chloro- compound.	
10. 2:6:dinitrophenol	Formed.	Formed	Reactive
11. 4-Bromo-2:6-dinitrophenol	"	"	"
12. 4-Iodo-2:6-dinitrophenol	"	"	"
13. 3-Chloro-4:6-dinitrophenol	"	"	"
14. 3-Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitrophenol	"	"	"
15. 3-Chloro-2-iodo-4:6-dinitrophenol	"	"	"
16. 3-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitrophenol	Not formed	"	...
17. 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-nitro-methylbenzoate	Formed	...	Partly reactive
18. 4-Hydroxy-3-nitromethylbenzoate	"	...	" "
19. 4-Hydroxy-5-bromo-3-nitro-methylbenzoate	"	...	" "
‡20. Dinitrothymol	"	...	Not reactive
‡21. Dinitrocarvacrol	"	...	"
‡22. 2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methyl-ethylbenzoate	"	...	Partly reactive

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